

BOLOMETRIC LUMINOSITY: AN INDEX TO SEYFERT GALAXY CLASSIFICATION

David Ifeanyichukwu Oyor

Science Laboratory Technology Department, Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana

Email: oyordavid@gmail.com

Abstract

The data used for this study were from a very large sample of Seyfert galaxies (217,272 galaxies) obtained from SDSS DR10 (Sloan Digital Sky Survey Data Release 10). Based on observed parameters, we computed the bolometric luminosity which enabled us classify these Seyfert galaxies into Seyfert 1s (188,486 galaxies) and Seyfert 2s (28,786 galaxies). Analyses on both the observed and computed parameters revealed that Seyfert 2 galaxies were less luminous than the Seyfert 1 galaxies and the region of broad line emission progressively declines from its high intensity in Seyfert 1s to the point of disappearance at sufficiently low bolometric luminosity (Seyfert 2s). Contrary to the standard unification scheme which posits that, the torus obscuration and the observer location are the only factors in determining the spectral class of any given AGN; it is possible that intrinsic broad line emission from Seyfert galaxies may follows an evolutionary trend from Seyfert 1 to Seyfert 2 as the bolometric luminosity of the AGN decreases.

Keywords: Seyfert galaxies, bolometric luminosity, hydrogen alpha, emission lines

Introduction

Seyfert galaxies are low luminosity active galactic nuclei that have an absolute B-band luminosity of $M_B > -21.51 + 5 \log h_0$ (Schmidt and Green, 1983), with h_0 denoting the Hubble constant in units of $100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. Seyfert galaxies are one of the two largest groups of active galaxies, along with quasars. They were the first type of active galaxy to be discovered (Whittle, 2006). They have similar nucleus like quasars (very luminous, distant and bright sources of electromagnetic radiation) with very high surface brightness whose spectra reveal strong, high-ionization emission lines, but unlike quasars, their host galaxies are clearly detectable (Petrov, 2004; Maiolino and Rieke, 1995).

Seyfert galaxies have extremely bright nuclei, with luminosities ranging between 10^8 and 10^{11} solar luminosities. Only about 5% of them are radio bright; their emissions are moderate in gamma rays and bright in X-rays (Peterson, 1997 and Popping, 2008). Their visible and infrared spectra show very bright emission lines of hydrogen, helium, nitrogen, and oxygen (Massi, 2013). These emission lines exhibit strong Doppler broadening, which implies velocities from 500 to $4,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and are believed to originate near an accretion disc surrounding the central black hole. The common characteristics and efficient ways to detect Seyfert galaxies include; looking specifically for galaxies with bright ultraviolet emission, bright x-ray emission, or unusual far-infrared colors (Whittle, 2006).

Seyfert galaxies account for about 10% of all galaxies (Maiolino and Rieke, 1995) and are some of the most intensely studied objects in astronomy, as they are thought to be powered by the same phenomena that occur in quasars, although they are closer and less luminous than quasars. These galaxies have super-massive black holes at their centers which are surrounded by accretion discs of in-falling material. The accretion discs are believed to be the source of the observed ultraviolet radiation. Ultraviolet emission and absorption lines provide the best diagnostics for the composition of the surrounding material (Davidsen, 1993).

Studying Seyfert galaxies in the visible light wave band reveals that most Seyfert galaxies look like normal spiral galaxies, but when studied under other wavelengths, it becomes clear that the luminosity of their cores is of comparable intensity to the luminosity of whole galaxies the size of the Milky Way (Soper, 2013). Over the years, more than 800 Seyfert galaxies have been discovered (Whittle, 2006). In gathering the spectrophotometric data for the Seyfert galaxies, it became obvious that not all spectra from Seyfert galaxies are identical. Seyfert galaxies were therefore classified according to the characteristics of their emission spectra (Goad et. al., 2012). A simple classification into types I and II has been devised, with the classes depending on the relative width of their emission lines (Weedman, 1973).

Emission Lines from Seyfert Galaxies

The emission lines seen on the spectrum of a Seyfert galaxy may come from the surface of the accretion disc itself, or may come from clouds of gas illuminated by the central engine in an ionization cone. The exact geometry of the emitting region is difficult to determine due to poor resolution of the galactic center. Nevertheless, each part of the accretion disc has a different velocity relative to our line of sight, and the faster the gas is rotating around the black hole, the broader the emission line will be (Goad et. al., 2012). The information contained in spectral lines allows us in the following:

1. To identify the chemical composition of the radiating material.
2. Gives us the information about the state of ionization or excitation of the material (relating to its temperature).
3. To obtain information about the velocity field of the atoms (temperature) and their relative motion along the line of sight.

Two types of emission line are observed from a number of astronomical objects. These are called permitted and forbidden lines. The radiative decays of hydrogen (the atom is de-excited by the emission of photons as the electron returns to the ground state, either in a single step, or perhaps in a number of steps if there are intermediate levels) produce permitted lines while forbidden lines are produced by an atom when it de-excites to a lower state in a particular environment, such as the rarefied vacuum of space. The presence of forbidden lines gives valuable information about the density and pressure of the medium in which the atom exists. The identification of forbidden lines is given by the ionized species enclosed in square brackets followed by the wavelengths in nanometers e.g. the doubly ionized oxygen line given by [OIII] 5007. The key factor is that per unit mass of gas, permitted lines have an emissivity that increases linearly with the density of the gas, whereas above critical density, forbidden lines have a constant emissivity. As the density of the gas increases, there is a corresponding increase in collisional excitation, and that implies that, the ratio of permitted line flux to forbidden line flux increases with increasing density and it becomes

more difficult to see the forbidden lines, but they are indeed present (Ian, 1996). The observation of permitted and forbidden lines forms one of the key methods by which the velocity dispersion of the Seyfert galaxies is being revealed.

The Sample

The data used in this study were obtained from SDSS DR10 (Sloan Digital Sky Survey Data Release 10, the paper for it is Ahn et. al. 2013, submitted to APJS and posted at arXiv: 1307.7735). The data consist of 217,272 Seyfert galaxies, with their observed parameters which includes; velocity dispersion, luminosity distance, and equivalent width and flux of hydrogen alpha ($H\alpha$). Based on the flux of hydrogen alpha, the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) was calculated. The data were classified into Seyfert 1 (188,486 galaxies) and Seyfert 2 (28,786 galaxies) based on their bolometric luminosities; $L_{bol} > L_{bol(threshold)}$ = Seyfert 1s, while $L_{bol} \leq L_{bol(threshold)}$ = Seyfert 2s .

Distribution of Bolometric Luminosity

Luminosity is the total amount of electromagnetic energy a body (star, galaxy or other astronomical object) radiates per unit of time. It is related to brightness, which is the luminosity of an object in a given spectral region. From the given data of the flux of hydrogen alpha ($H\alpha$) and the luminosity distance, the luminosity of the Seyfert galaxies was estimated using the formula below;

$$F = L/4\pi D_L^2 \quad (1)$$

where F is the flux of $H\alpha$, D_L is the luminosity distance and L is the luminosity of the narrow $H\alpha$ line $L(H\alpha)$. Following Laor (2003), the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) was calculated for the sources from the luminosity of the narrow $H\alpha$ line as indicated in equation 2;

$$\log L_{bol} = 1.176 \log L(H\alpha) - 4.91 \quad (2)$$

The distribution of logarithm of the bolometric luminosity of the Seyfert galaxies are given in figures 1 – 3. There is a noticeable difference between the mean of log of bolometric luminosities of the Seyfert galaxies. The distribution of the whole sample is shown in figure 1, with mean log of bolometric luminosity 44.12 and standard deviation of 0.9830. The Seyfert 1s and 2s (figures 2 and 3) have the mean log of their bolometric luminosity as 44.25 and 43.31 with standard deviations 0.8579 and 1.305 respectively. These results indicate that the Seyfert 1s are more luminous than the Seyfert 2s.

Fig. 1 Distribution of Log of Bolometric Luminosity for both Seyfert 1s and 2s

Fig. 2 Distribution of Log of Bolometric Luminosity for Seyfert 1s

Fig. 3 Distribution of Log of Bolometric Luminosity for Seyfert 2s

Classification of Seyfert Galaxies

Because Seyfert galaxies are characterized by strong and broad emission lines, the nature of these emission lines was used as the classification criterion. Seyfert galaxies are classified according to the emission lines shown by their spectra as; Seyfert 1 galaxies (S1s) showing both broad and narrow emission lines and Seyfert 2 galaxies (S2s) showing only narrow emission lines (Ricci et. al., 2011). For the purpose of this work, the classification will be based on their bolometric luminosities and emphasis will only be laid on Seyfert 1 and 2 galaxies. According to Elitzur et. al., (2014), there is a threshold bolometric luminosity which determines the appearance and disappearance of the broad line region (BLR). This is given by, $L_{\text{bol}(\text{threshold})} = 5 \times 10^{39} \mathfrak{m}^{2/3} \text{ ergs}^{-1}$, where $\mathfrak{m} = M_{\text{BH}}/10^7 M_{\odot}$, and M_{BH} is the black hole mass of the object and M_{\odot} is the mass of the Sun. Seyfert galaxies with bolometric luminosities greater than the threshold bolometric luminosity are classified as Seyfert 1s while those less than or equal the threshold bolometric luminosity are the Seyfert 2s.

Seyfert 1 Galaxies

Seyfert 1 galaxies (S1s) are galaxies with bolometric luminosities greater than the threshold bolometric luminosity ($5 \times 10^{39} \mathfrak{m}^{2/3} \text{ ergs}^{-1}$), they are very bright sources of ultraviolet light and X-rays (Bremer, 2014), in addition to the visible light coming from their cores. They have two sets of emission lines on their spectra: narrow emission lines with widths (measured in velocity units) of several hundred kilometers per second, and broad lines with widths up to 10^4 kms^{-1} . The broad emission lines which are indicative of a central concentration of hot gas that is expanding at speeds of up to thousands of kilometers per second (Hodge, 2024), originate above the accretion disc of the super-massive black hole thought to power the galaxy, while the narrow lines occur beyond

the broad line region of the accretion disc. Both emissions are caused by heavily ionized gas (Armitage, 2004).

Seyfert 2 Galaxies

Seyfert 2 galaxies (S2s) are galaxies that are less than or equal the threshold bolometric luminosity ($5 \times 10^{39} \text{ m}^{2/3} \text{ ergs}^{-1}$). They have a characteristic bright core which also appears bright even when viewed at the infrared wavelengths (Siobahn, 2013). Their spectra contain only narrow emission lines (but still wider than emission lines in normal galaxies), which indicates that they have very low velocities associated with them (Hodge, 2024). In S2s, both permitted and forbidden lines were about equal with velocity ranging up to about 1000 kms^{-1} . These narrow lines are due to low density gas clouds at larger distances (than the broad line clouds) from the nucleus. In Seyfert 2 galaxies, unlike the S1s, their X-ray radiation appears to be absorbed by material in the line of sight (LOS) between the object and the observer (Hodge, 2024).

Discussions

Here, the observed differences or similarities in both the given and the estimated parameters are deployed to ascertain the nature of the classes of Seyfert galaxies. From the distributions, we noticed a distinct difference in the mean values of the bolometric luminosity between Seyfert 1s and 2s. This reveals the nature of Seyfert 2s as being less luminous massive with a less detectable narrow line $\text{EW}_{\text{H}\alpha}$ than the Seyfert 1s.

Table 1 shows distribution statistics for the parameters and Table 2 is the correlation values for all the Seyfert galaxies (S_{ALL}) (217,272 galaxies), the Seyfert 1 galaxies (S1s) (188,486 galaxies) and the Seyfert 2 galaxies (S2s) (28,786 galaxies).

Table 1 Distribution of Parameters for the Seyfert Galaxies

Parameters	Mean			Standard Deviation		
	S _{ALL}	S1s	S2s	S _{ALL}	S1s	S2s
L_{bol} (solar units)	44.121	44.246	43.309	0.983	0.858	1.305
σ (kms^{-1})	210.53	197.48	295.99	76.44	56.69	121.03
Log $\text{EW}_{\text{H}\alpha}$	1.3044	1.7037	0.2285	0.8742	0.7797	1.060

Table 2 Correlations of Parameters for the Seyfert Galaxies

Variables	S _{ALL}	S1s	S2s
σ and L_{bol}	0.147	0.259	0.515
EW_H α and L_{bol}	0.246	0.374	0.172
EW_H α and σ	0.004	0.008	0.119

A superficial look at table 1 reveals that the velocity dispersion for the Seyfert 2 galaxies are higher than that of Seyfert 1s, and this yields to a stronger positive correlation with the bolometric luminosity in S2s than S1s (table 2). The equivalent width of hydrogen alpha for the S1s are higher than that of S2s (table 3.1), and there is a more positive correlation between the equivalent width of hydrogen alpha and the bolometric luminosity in S1s than S2s (table 2), showing that the narrow line EW_H α are more detectable in S1s than in S2s.

Our results show that, there is a decrease in its bolometric luminosity and the region of broad line emission progressively declines from its high intensity in Seyfert 1s to the point of disappearance at sufficiently low bolometric luminosity (Seyfert 2s). Contrary to the standard unification scheme which posits that, the torus obscuration and the observer location are the only factors in determining the spectral class of any given AGN; it is possible that intrinsic broad line emission from Seyfert galaxies may follows an evolutionary trend from Seyfert 1 to Seyfert 2 as accretion unto the supermassive black hole is decreasing. This possible evolutionary trend suggests that an AGN seen today as Seyfert 1 might in future be seen as Seyfert 2 based on the increase in black hole mass as well as decrease in the bolometric luminosity of the AGN.

References

- Ahn, C. P., Alexandroff, R., Prieto, C. A., Anders, F., Anderson, S. F., Anderton, T., ... & Oravetz, D. J. (2013). The Tenth Data Release of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey: First Spectroscopic Data from the SDSS-III Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1307.7735*.
- Armitage, P. (2004). *Astrophysics 2, Lecture 27: Active galaxies – The Unified Model*. ASTR 3830 Lecture notes, University of Colorado Boulder.
- Elitzur, M., Ho, L. C., & Trump, J. R. (2014). Evolution of broad-line emission from active galactic nuclei. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 438(4), 3340-3351.
- Goad, M. R., Korista, K. T., Ruff, A. J. (2012). The Broad Emission Line Region: The Confluence of the Outer Accretion Disc with the Inner Edge of the Dusty Torus. *MNRAS*, 426 (4), 3086 – 3111.
- Hodge, P.W. (2024, February 1). Seyfert galaxy. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/science/Seyfert-galaxy>
- Ian, R. (1996). *Active Galactic Nuclei*. John Wiley and Sons in association with Praxis Publishing Ltd, New York.

- Laor, A. (2003). On the nature of low-luminosity narrow-line active galactic nuclei. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 590(1), 86.
- Maiolino, R. & Rieke, G. H. (1995). Low-Luminosity and Obscured Seyfert Nuclei in Nearby Galaxies. *Astrophysical Journal* 454; 95 – 105.
- Massi, M. (2013). *Active Galaxies*. Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy.
- Petrov, G. T. (2004) (ed). *Active Galaxy Nuclei*. Bulgarian Academy of Science/Institute of Astronomy.
- Popping, G. (2008). *AGN Host Galaxies and their Environment*. University of Groningen.
- Ricci, C., Walter, R., Courvoisier, T. J.-L., & Paltani, S. (2011). Reflection in Seyfert Galaxies and the Unified Model of AGN. *A&A*, 532, A102.
- Schmidt, M. & Green, R. F. (1983). Quasar Evolution derived from the Palomar Bright Quasar Survey and other Complete Quasar Surveys. *Astrophysical Journal, Part 1*, 269, 352-374
- Siobahn, M. (2013). *Distance and Weird galaxies: Astronomy Course Notes and Supplementary Material*. University of Northern IOWA.
- Soper, D. E. (2013). *Seyfert Galaxies*. University of Oregon.
- Weedman, D. W. (1973). A Photometric study of Markarian galaxies. *Astrophysical Journal*, 183, 29-40.
- Whittle, M. (2006). *Seyfert Galaxies: Encyclopedia of Astronomy and Astrophysics*. IOP Publishing Ltd.